

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INDIVIDUAL CHARACTERISTICS OF STUDENTS OF A HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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Abstract:

This article deals with the pedagogical conditions for the development of individual characteristics of students in higher establishments. In addition, author provides several propositions of prominent researchers who contributed in the sphere of pedagogy and psychology.

Key words: individualization, supra-professional, pedagogical conditions, intellectual abilities, intelligence, motive

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The modern Uzbek education system is being formed in new socio-economic conditions, which cause changes in the requirements for graduates of higher educational institutions. High-quality training of an engineer is inextricably linked with the need to develop clear requirements for the general cultural and professional competencies of graduates of technical universities, which would allow them to quickly adapt to work, creatively approach any changes in the labor market. Therefore, the higher institution faces a task that would create conditions for the development of professional competencies of students and individualize the approach to students. This, in turn, leads to the education of an active, initiative, independent professional, striving to improve his cultural and professional level, and as a result will form the system engineering thinking of the future specialist. At the same time, the organization of the educational process, taking into account the individual characteristics of students, allows creating optimal conditions for realizing the potential of each student.

Currently, significant aspects of the problem of individualization of learning are analyzed in the scientific works of I.E. Unt, according to which individualization is not realized in the entire scope of educational activity, but episodically or in some kind of educational work and is integrated with non-individualized work [1]. An important aspect in the individualization of the learning process is the Olympiads, which stimulate the development of new methods, means and forms of learning and intellectual development of students. Conducting student Olympiads is a powerful incentive for the formation of general cultural and professional competencies and motivation in the process of teaching students.

In his scientific works, E.F. Zeer argues that in connection with the modernization of education, changes in the field of psychology make it necessary for a specialist to form "special supra-professional, more precisely, extra-functional knowledge, skills, properties, qualities and abilities that ensure his professional mobility, competitiveness and social

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security” [2]. At the same time K.E. Andreev he believes that “the needs of the modern labor market for the quality of vocational education are based on professional socialization and adaptation at all stages of the acquired status (entrant, student, graduate – young specialist, and subsequently a professional motivated to improve their professional level throughout their working life)” [3].

The teaching staff is faced with the task of creating pedagogical conditions containing a system of scientific and theoretical knowledge that would form professional competencies. The solution to this problem is the didactic principle, which provides for an individual approach at the subjective level, since the implementation of an individual approach involves the purposeful construction of the educational process. The task of implementing the modernization of education in the higher education system in order to improve the quality of training of technical specialists is one of the most relevant in the theory and methodology of higher education [4].

In the process of forming scientific and theoretical knowledge, the level of development of intellectual abilities increases, which allows the student to effectively solve new life and professional problems, especially of a global nature, namely: to be open to new things; to approach emerging problems realistically, to see them in all their complexity, inconsistency and diversity; to have broad and flexible thinking, see alternative solutions and overcome existing stereotypes; critically analyze experience, be able to learn lessons from the past.

According to modern ideas about the essence of the teaching, the student must manage his own cognitive activity: plan the pace and trajectory of the teaching, initiate the need to provide him with consulting services, determine for himself the time and order of passing the current control (self-control).

Nature-like teaching is a self-managed, independent educational-cognitive and educational-practical activity of a student.

Psychology and pedagogy can approach the optimization of the educational process from different positions: improving teaching methods, developing new principles for building curricula and textbooks, improving the work of deans, creating a psychological service in universities, individualizing the learning and upbringing process, provided that the individual characteristics of the student are more fully taken into account, etc. In all these approaches, the central link is the personality the student. Knowledge of the psychological characteristics of a student's personality – abilities, general intellectual development, interests, motives, character traits, temperament, working capacity, self-awareness, etc. - allows us to find real opportunities to take them into account in the conditions of modern mass education in higher education. On the success of students' studies in higher educational institutions many factors influence: financial situation, health status, age, marital status, level of pre-university training, possession of skills of self-organization, planning and control of one's activities (primarily educational), motives for choosing a university, adequacy of initial ideas about the specifics of university education; form of study (full-time, evening, correspondence, distance, etc.), the availability of tuition fees and its amount, the organization of the educational process at the university, the material base of the university, the level of qualification teachers and staff, the prestige of the university and, finally, the individual psychological characteristics of students.

Why do some students work a lot and willingly on mastering knowledge and professional skills, and the difficulties that arise only add to their energy and desire to achieve their goals, while others do everything as if from under a stick, and the appearance of any significant obstacles sharply reduces their activity up to the destruction of educational activities?

Such differences can be observed under the same external conditions of educational activity (socio-economic situation, organization and methodological support of the educational process, teacher qualifications, etc.).

When explaining this phenomenon, psychologists and teachers most often appeal to such individual psychological characteristics of students as the level of intelligence (the ability to assimilate knowledge, skills, and successfully apply them to solve problems), creativity (the ability to develop new knowledge yourself); educational motivation, which provides strong positive experiences when achieving educational goals, high self-esteem, leading to the formation of a high level of claims, etc.

But none of these qualities alone, or even their combination, is sufficient to guarantee the formation of a student's attitude to everyday, persistent and hard work to master professional and social competence in conditions of fairly frequent or prolonged failures that are inevitable in any complex activity.

Recently, social intelligence has been singled out in psychology as a relatively independent type, understood as a set of abilities underlying communicative competence (competence in communication), which provides successful solution of the tasks of adequate perception of a person by a person, establishing and maintaining contacts with other people, influencing them, ensuring joint activities, occupying a decent position in the team and society (social status). A high level of social intelligence is important for mastering professions of the "man-man" type, according to the classification of E.A. Klimov. At the same time, there is evidence that a high level of social intelligence sometimes develops as a compensation for a low level of development of subject (general) intelligence and creativity. In favor of the fact that a high level of social intelligence often correlates with a low level of learning success, some typologies of students' personality are also recorded, which will be discussed below. However, the formal academic performance of such students may be overstated due to skillful influence on teachers in order to obtain the desired higher institution.

As the authors of one of the most extensive studies of the psychological characteristics of students note, the main factor determining the success of educational activity is not the severity of individual mental personality traits, but their structure, in which volitional qualities play a leading role [5]. According to V.A. Ivannikov, a person shows his strong-willed qualities when he performs an action that is initially insufficiently motivated, i.e. inferior to other actions in the struggle for a "behavioral exit". The mechanism of volitional action can be called the replenishment of the lack of implementation motivation due to the intentional strengthening of the motive of this action and the weakening of the motives of competing actions. This is possible, in particular, by giving the action a new meaning. The big problem is to build the educational process in such a way that the student has to overcome himself as little as possible, force him to get involved in educational activities. It seems that it is impossible to completely exclude the need to appeal to the strong-willed qualities of a student, but it is also unacceptable to blame all the problems and shortcomings in the organization of the educational process on laziness and lack of will of students. The motive for learning should lie within the learning activity itself or as close as possible to its process. This can be achieved in this way: to make the learning process as interesting as possible for the student, bringing him satisfaction and even pleasure; to help the student to form such motives and attitudes that will allow him to experience satisfaction from overcoming internal and external obstacles in learning activities.

By researching pedagogical phenomena, the teacher organizes not only his professional knowledge, forms his pedagogical style, personal and professional outlook, but

also individualizes the approach to the formation of professional competencies. It is advisable to start systematic scientific and methodological work on the individualization of tasks as early as possible, study the most pressing problems of preparing students for scientific research, consider them from different positions and with different levels of study and eventually take part in student Olympiads of various levels.

References:

- [1]. Унт И.Э. *Индивидуализация и дифференциация обучения*. Москва: «Педагогика» 1990: Р. 46 – 48.
- [2]. Зеер Э.Ф. *Психология профессионального образования: учебник для студентов учреждений высшего профессионального образования*. Москва: Издательский центр «Академия», 2013.
- [3]. Андреев К.Е. *Роль метода проектов в формировании профессиональных компетенций*. Специалист. 2012; № 2.
- [4]. Дралюк И.А., Дралюк Р.С. *Повышение качества подготовки специалиста как условие его конкурентоспособности. Теория и практика образования в современном мире: материалы VI Международной научной конференции*. Санкт-Петербург, 2014: 297 – 300.
- [5]. Иванников В.А. *Психологические механизмы волевой регуляции*. – М., 1991
- [6]. Matatyusufovna A. U. *Descriptive means of creating female characters in the works of gerbert bates //Journal of Positive School Psychology*. – 2022. – С. 9295-9299.
- [7]. Fakhriddinovna H. L. *Improving the research skills of teachers through revitalized research and development program //asia pacific journal of marketing & management review ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603*. – 2023. – Т. 12. – №. 02. – С. 29-33.
- [8]. Ismatova M. S. *Use of coaching technologies in auditorium training //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences*. – 2023. – С. 1-5.